

Bridgmanite is nearly dry at the top of the lower mantle

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Highlights

- We synthesized high-quality single crystals of bridgmanite up to 300 μm in size
- Bridgmanite crystals contain less than 50 ppm wt.H₂O at the uppermost lower mantle
- The majority of the top of a pyrolitic lower mantle is nearly dry